

What Does It Mean to Be Happy?: The Notion of Happiness in Terry Pratchett's Series of *Johnny Maxwell* (1992-1996) and *Tiffany Aching* (2003-2010)

This paper aims to explore the notion of happiness as portrayed in the series of *Johnny Maxwell* (1992-1996) and *Tiffany Aching* (2003-2010) by Terry Pratchett. Taken out of Pratchett's corpus of children's fiction, these two series are selected because the two protagonists' predicaments and understanding of happiness experience shifts throughout the series, parallel to their growing up. By comparing their personal characteristics, the predicaments they find themselves in and what they classify as making them happy, this paper seeks to examine Pratchett's portrayals of children's perceptions of happiness as well as sources of unhappiness and how these affect their lives in the contemporary world.

Timothy J. Sharp (2009)ⁱ wrote that there is nothing "mystical or magical" (2) when it comes to happiness. Instead, happiness is made up of choices that people make using various methods of dealing with their life and the world on a daily basis. Johnny is portrayed as being emotionally affected by his parents' separation. While Johnny does not actively seek alternative ways to be happy, he finds it satisfactory and even enjoyable when he gets to solve the problems that he stumbles upon; his satisfaction proven by his positive note at the end of each book.

Tiffany, a teenaged witch, finds any oppression as upsetting. She deliberately decides to become a witch so that she could rectify this social malaise. Tiffany's happiness is more explicitly portrayed as her success in defending the powerless and the abused. Johnny and Tiffany are polar opposites but this notion of attaining happiness via unselfish acts is the one particular point that makes them similar. By relating to this, this paper therefore aims to examine the significance of the pursuit of happiness to the characters' process of growing up and understanding the world they live in.

ⁱ Sharp, Timothy J. *100 Ways to Happy Children: A Guide for Busy Parents*. London: Penguin Books, 2009. Print.